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CURRENT PRACTICE OF DESIGN PROMOTION ACTIVITIES AND ITS INFLUENTIAL FACTORS

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ABSTRACT

It is obvious that promoting design is considered as important in many countries. There are many design promotion organisations worldwide and each organisation manages a different set of activities for promoting design. However, as each organisation deals with different social and economic contexts, any similar activity can have different results. This means there are certain factors arising from various contexts which influence the management of design promotion. In order to manage design promotion in a strategic way, it is necessary to understand what kinds of influential factors exist and how the factors influence their management. Therefore, a survey on design promotion was carried out to establish the current phenomena. With the result of the survey, how the design promotion activities are varied, what factors are importantly considered and what barriers can affect design promotion will be discussed in this paper.

Keywords: design promotion, promoting design, design support, design management.

BACKGROUND

Design promotion is implemented based on the fundamental assumption that it promotes the use of design in a strategic way. With this assumption, design promotion aims to enhance not only sustainable growth of economic competitiveness but also better quality of society, (Hannon, 1993; Hytönen, 2003; Cawood, 2004; Sung et al 2006; Bichard, 2008; Park and Chung 2008) and design promotion organisations (DPOs) manage a set of activities to achieve these aims

Most design promotion system and its activities are similar to many nations and DPOs (Hytönen, 2003). However, as each DPO faces particular national conditions in social, economic and policy context, any similar activity is likely to have different results from country to county. So it is assumed that there would be certain factors influence the management of design promotion. The factors, for example, can be design promotion policy from the government or design maturity of the society, and those factors can have a strong influence on DPOs managing their activities (Park, Nam & Chung, 2010).

It is clear that there is no one ideal system which covers all ranges of design promotion issues. However, by analysing the current phenomena of design promotion and its influential factors, it is possible to suggest what each DPO should consider more, and how the barriers should be managed, so that they can strategically develop an adequate design promotion scheme which successfully achieves their aims of design promotion.

In this paper, as a part, what kinds of design promotion activities currently each DPOs focus, what factors strongly influence the management of the activities, and what kind of barriers each DPOs deal with were surveyed. Identification of relationship between design promotion activities and the influential factors makes possible to be able to manage design promotion activities in strategic ways. It is expected that this study would suggest a milestone for DPOs to clarify their situation and help to set a design promotion model for the near future.

RESEARCH AIMS AND METHOD

The aim of this research is to analyse the phenomena of design promotion activities as well as the main factors in the management such activities. The specific aims are as follows:

- Aim 1. To explore the priorities of design promotion activities in each Design Promotion Organisation (DPO).
- Aim 2. To explore how importantly influential factors are considered in the management of design promotion.
- Aim 3. To identify the factors that act as barriers to design promotion.
- Aim 4. To identify the relationship between the activities and its influential factors.

A survey method was used to achieve the aims of this research. DSOs from around the world were asked to share information on their current management of design promotion activities and on the effect of the main factors on design promotion activities.

KEY ACTIVITIES & INFLUENTIAL FACTORS

KEY DESIGN PROMOTION ACTIVITIES

In order to survey the current activity priorities in design promotion, it is necessary to identify key activities.

Most design promotion organisations seem to classify design promotion activities into two main types: 'design support' and 'design promotion'. The former provides the client with individual assistance, while the latter addresses a broader audience with more general interactions (Tether, 2003). In contrast, Sung et al (2007) defines design promotion at a broader level. Tether distinguishes the notion of design support and design promotion as different types of design promotion activities, adding to the confusion that both design 'support' and 'promotion' become subsets of 'design promotion', while Sung et al's definition seems to include the notion of design support within 'design promotion'.

Figure 1. Four types of activities in design promotion, proposed by Park & Chung, 2007

Design promotion may include all relevant activities of helping any client, private and public, to achieve their goals in through design. However, it seems that Tether idea of design promotion is more narrowly defined than what 'promotion' means. Moreover, the current classification of design promotion does not include various demands from the public sector such as dealing with social problems, public services.

According to Park & Chung (2007), a type of design promotion activities can be determined by the clients and methods of design promotion activity.

- Client: private/public sector;
- Method: direct/indirect.

With these criteria, a typology of design promotion was proposed which includes four types of design promotion (see Figure.1). Based on the proposed typology, Park & Chung (2007) also identified 3 key activities of the each type. In total, 12 key design promotion activities identified [Table 1].

- Design Support: Directly helping companies use design in project level.
- Design Encouragement: Indirectly encouraging companies use design in strategic way.
- Design Enlightenment: Enlightening and educating general public to increase design awareness.
- Design Furtherance: Based on high design awareness, providing the environment to let clients solve social issues or problems

In order to manage survey questionnaire, Park's 12 key design promotion activities were adapted to investigate the current activity priorities.

Promotion Type	Key Activity
Design Support	Financial support to clients
	Counseling / Advisory services
	Connecting clients to designers, design firms
Design Encouragement	Design Awards / Certifications
	Education programmes (Lecture/Seminar)
	Design workshops
Design Enlightenment	Public events (Design festival / Campaign)
	Education programmes for citizens
	Design shop, library, exhibitions
Design Furtherance	Policy making for public authorities
	Participating in design projects for public facilities / services
	Participating in design projects for community

Table 1. 12 key activities of design promotion, identified by Park and Chung, 2007.

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE MANAGEMENT OF DESIGN PROMOTION

Various factors influence the management of design promotion but the task of identifying the main factors is difficult because each DPO operates in a unique context. According to Park et al. (2010), factors that influence the DPOs’ management can be identified through the historical analysis of the changes in design promotion activities. By investigating the changes in activities and analysing the factors that caused the change, the influential factors can be identified. As a result of the historical

analysis, he proposed 4 internal and 7 external influential factors. Internal factors that influence inside organisation and external factors that influence outside organisation [Figure 2]. The 11 factors identified by Park et al. appear to have the strongest influence on the management of design promotion. For that reason, the questions in the survey are based on those 11 factors.

SURVEY DESIGN

SURVEY STRUCTURE

The survey consists of four different parts.

- Part1: priorities of currently managed activities,
- Part2: influential factors that are importantly considered and factors that acts as barriers in the current management of the activities,
- Part3: further management of activities
- Part4: organisation information data.

12 key design promotion activities (see Table 1) adapted in the survey questionnaire to ask current activity priorities.

Eleven main influential factors were used in two different ways in the survey. Firstly, the respondents were asked to comment on the importance of the 11 main factors with regard to the management of current activities [Table 2, Left column]. They were then asked to state how the main factors hindered the management of activities [Table 2, Right column].

Figure 2. Factors that influence the management of design promotion, identified by Park Chung and Nam, 2010. .

Our organisation importantly consider...	... act(s) as barrier(s) in design promotion
Sustainable external funding	Lack of external funding
Sustainable self-generated incomes	Unstable profit from our activities
Government policy or national design promotion policy	Pressure from outside organisation
Design awareness in the general public	Lack of design awareness in the public
Clients' design maturity when we provide design related supports	Lack of design maturity of clients
National economic situation	Unstable national economic situation
Development of our own design promotion policy	Inappropriate policy or strategy in organisation
Adequate organisation structure to implement our activities	Inefficient organisation structure /political issues in organisation
Staff skills and allocation of the ability into proper activities	Lack of manpower
Demands from clients	Too many demands from clients
Relationship between other related organisations	Lack of relationship with other related organisations

Table 2. Influential factors when those are importantly considered and those act as barriers.

The last part on information about the organisation included questions on staff numbers, the year of establishment, and the type of organisation. These questions were used to group the organisations for further analysis.

SELECTION OF SAMPLES

Fifty-three DPOs were selected for the survey. The respondents were people in various positions of responsibility for the management of design promotion activities, such as CEOs, directors, senior researchers, project managers, and policy development managers. They were contacted via e-mail and phone calls.

COLLECTION OF DATA

Since participants (DPOs) were located around the world, an Internet-based questionnaire was developed for the easy accessibility. The survey was designed in three different languages for participants' convenience: English, Korean and Japanese versions. A pilot test was conducted twice to confirm the appropriateness and ease of administering the questionnaire. Of the 53 DPOs contacted, 34 (or 64%) responded to the survey, though two were excluded owing to problems with their responses. Thus, the survey analysis is based on the responses of 32 respondents. The respondents included 13 DPOs from Asia, two from South America, one from New Zealand and 16 from Europe. The participating DPOs are listed in Appendix.

CURRENT PRACTICE OF DESIGN PROMOTION

ACTIVITY PRIORITIES

In the survey, the respondents rated the 12 nominated activities on a scale of one to five (where one means "very low priority" and five means "very high priority"; and the term "not applicable" (N/A) was used for any activity that the DPO was not currently managing). A descriptive analysis of the survey results reveals how the respondents prioritise their activities. According to the Standard Deviation (S.D.) value comparison, activity priorities are different from organisation to organisation [Table 3].

Design Promotion Activities		N	M.	S. D.
Support	Financial support to client companies	32	1.531	1.796
	Counseling/Advisory services	32	4.188	1.060
	Connecting client to design firms	32	4.063	1.014
Encouragement	Design awards/Certification	32	3.500	1.666
	Education for client company (Seminars)	32	3.969	1.257
	Design workshops	32	4.250	.879
Enlightenment	Public design events (design festival)	32	3.688	1.378
	Education programmes for citizens	32	2.781	1.338
	Managing a design, exhibition, library	32	2.813	1.655
Furtherance	Developing design policy for the public	32	3.375	1.621
	Projects for public services/facilities	32	3.438	1.268
	Projects to solve social problems/issues	32	3.344	1.473

Table Table 3. Descriptive statistics for the priorities of design promotion activities .

This comparison revealed that most DPOs have high priorities in Design Workshops, Counseling/Advisory services, and Connecting clients to appropriate designers or design firms. It means most DPOs consider those activities as essential for design promotion.

In comparison, following four types of activities such as Financial support to clients, Design awards/Certifications, Managing design shop/library/exhibition, and Developing design policy for the public, have different priorities among DPOs as the S.D. value are relatively higher than other activities. It is assumed that activity priorities are different from DPO to DPO and those DPOs can be classified into a similar group based on the priorities.

Different Activity Priorities among DPOs

In order to identify how activity priorities are different among the DPOs, DPOs were classified by the priorities. A hierarchical cluster analysis and k-means cluster analysis resulted in the classification of the DPOs into two groups in every type of design promotion. The four types of design promotion adapted in this paper were used (See Figure 1). An independent T-test analysis was managed to check each group shows meaningful differences. As a result, it was identified that there are nine types of DPOs and DPOs in a same type seem to manage similar activities. Table 4 shows the nine types of DPOs with their activity priorities. This result confirms that DPOs manage different sets of the activities and different priorities in their activities to achieve their specific goals in design promotion. [Table. 4]

Type	Financial support (Support)	Awards (Encouragement)	Enlightenment	Furtherance	Type of DPO
1	High	High	High	Low	Hong Kong Design Center Singapore Design Council Buenos Aires Design Center
2	High	High	Low	Low	Busan Design Center Toyama Design Center Daegu Design Center Better by Design
3	High	Low	High	Low	Gwangju Design Center
4	Low	High	High	High	Design Seoul Foundation DISEÑO+DISEÑO Barcelona Design Centre Institute of Industrial Design, Poland ACPI, France
5	Low	High	High	Low	JIDPO Nagoya Design Center Osaka Design Center Malaysia Design Council Design Flanders
6	Low	High	Low	High	KIDP Norwegian Design Council Norsk Form Design Forum Finland Hungarian Design Council
7	Low	High	Low	Low	Danish Design Center Svensk Form
8	Low	Low	High	Low	Thailand Creative & Design Center
9	Low	Low	Low	High	Design Council, UK Design Wales Centre for Design Innovation, Ireland Flanders InShape Swedish Industrial Design Foundation Estonian Design Center

Table 4. Nine types of DPOs based on Activity Priorities.

Figure 3. Examples of DPO types based on activity priority.

It is necessary to compare the difference in the activity priorities in order to understand the real context which each DPO type is dealing with.

Figure 3 shows examples of different activity priorities. The activities coloured with dark-grey represent the activities that are considered importantly in most DPOs. For instance, DPOs in the type 5 manage a range of activities to promote both for the private sector and public design awareness. In the case of the type 5, promoting design is considered as not only for the development of economy, but also better quality of society.

DPOs in the type 9 show strong priorities of design furtherance, which aims to promote design for the public services, policy, or social issues. Although they directly manage various activities for their profit clients, mostly SMEs, they rather favor to act as policy or strategy developers, knowledge centres, or liaisons between designers and client companies. As described above, there are various types of DPOs and they manage different activities with different priorities. It may explain the DPOs have different perspectives on design promotion or deal with different social and economic conditions.

Therefore, it is required to identify what kinds of contexts they are dealing with, how those contexts influence the DPOs, and lastly, what are the consequences of the management of their own design promotion activities.

FACTORS TO BE CONSIDERED

Most DPOs attach a high level of importance to the design capabilities of corporate clients, the design promotion policy or strategy of their own organisation, the adequacy of their human resources and staff capabilities, design awareness of the general public, industrial and corporate demand, and national economic conditions. The evidence for this observation can be found in the results of the descriptive analysis in Table 5. The following factors are considered the least important of the 11 main factors: sustainable self-generated income; sustainable external funding; adherence to government policy; and appropriate organisational structure.

However, the relatively high standard deviation in the statistics means there is no simple reason why these factors are considered to be the least important; the reasons appear to vary from DPO to DPO.

Factors importantly Considered	Mean	S.D.
Sustainable external funding	3.125	1.862
Sustainable self-generated incomes	2.375	1.680
Following government policy	3.500	1.722
Public design awareness	4.281	1.023
Design capability of client companies	4.531	.621
National economic condition	4.094	.856
Design promotion policy/strategy inside the organisation	4.375	.707
Appropriate organisation structure	3.844	.919
Appropriate staff ability / manpower	4.250	.762
Demands from clients or industries	4.250	.879
Partnerships with other related organisations, associations	4.156	1.050

Table 5. Descriptive Analysis of importantly considered influential Factors in design promotion.

The DPOs have diverse attitudes towards four factors: namely, sustainable external funding; sustainable self-generated income; adherence to government policy; and partnerships with other related organisations. These factors are important for some DPOs but not for others. Most DPOs seem to have a common view on the importance of some particular factors but diverse views on other factors. The diversity of views may be attributed to the unique socioeconomic and political circumstances of each DPO.

The DPOs were classified in an effort to shed light on their diverse opinions and priorities. They were put into the following three groups on the basis of their independence from the government:

- Group 1: Governmental DPOs which are fully funded by the government
- Group 2: Private organisations with government fund or DPOs belong to the government without financial support
- Group 3: Fully private organisations

Figure 4 compares the mean value of the four main factors for these three groups. The three groups view the factor of sustainable self-generated income in a

similar manner but they view the other three main factors in a different manner. DPOs that are more independent of government control or government funding tend to place less priority on sustainable external funding and adherence to government policy but more priority on partnerships with other related organisations, such as clients, design associations, and other DPOs. Correlation analysis was used to determine the relation between the degree of independence from the government and the main factors. The results of the correlation analysis reveal that DPOs that depend on the government tend to place a high priority on the government’s design-related policy and may strongly depend on the government as a source of sustainable external funding.

Figure 4. Mean value comparison of the considered factors based on 3 DPO groups.

In conclusion, DPOs prioritise the importance of various factors involved in the management of design promotion. Most of the respondents assigned a high level of importance to a small cluster of the 11 main factors, particularly staff capabilities, public awareness of design, and the design capabilities of clients. There was more variation in the level of importance assigned to the other factors. One contributing reason for this variation appears to be the degree of the independence from the government. Further study is needed to analyse the context of each factor and to clarify how each factor affects design promotion activities.

BARRIERS TO DESIGN PROMOTION

11 influential factors are also surveyed to ask how much of the influential factors are considered as barriers in the management of design promotion activities. It seems financial issues and clients' design capability come to most difficult barriers. The descriptive analysis revealed that DPOs experienced difficulties because of lack of external funding, lack of clients' design capacity, lack of manpower and staff ability, and lack of self-generated incomes.

To identify how these various barriers in design promotion relate with one another, factor analysis was employed (i.e., a principal component extraction method with varimax rotation), as well as Kaiser criterion with an Eigenvalue greater than one, in conjunction with evaluation of screen plots to determine the appropriate number of factors. Table 6 shows the summary of the results of factor analysis for the "11 influential as barriers". Three components which are strongly related with similar barrier factors were identified, and these accounted for 68.275 % of the total variance.

The first component, which scored for four related barrier factors, was designated "barriers arise inside DPO as an organisational problem". The second, with four barrier factors, was designated "barriers arise from clients or other organisations". The third component, with three barrier factors, was named as "environmental barriers that DPOs cannot control or manage". These three components can show three levels of barriers. The component 1 seems to be in matters of organizational issues and the component 2 matters relationship between DPO and other parties including clients and other DPO, designers associations, or design related organisations. The component 3 seems about environmental level around the DPO.

RECENT CHANGES IN DPO ACTIVITIES

The context of design promotion can be understood in two ways: by viewing the main factors as either important priorities or fatal barriers and by analysing organisational changes in DPOs.

Factors considered as barriers	Mean	S.D.	component		
			1	2	3
Inefficient organisation structure	3.667	1.373	0.834	0.248	0.115
Lack of manpower / lack of staff's ability	3.300	1.489	0.821	0.069	0.131
Inappropriate policy or strategy inside organisation	2.833	1.289	0.788	0.226	-0.03
Handling too many demands from clients or industries	2.833	1.085	0.525	0.352	0.337
Lack of clients' design capabilities	3.467	1.196	0.104	0.874	-0.095
Lack of public design awareness	2.933	1.202	0.123	0.810	0.231
Lack of self-generated income	2.633	1.066	0.267	0.720	0.206
Lack of partnership with other related organisations	2.567	1.331	0.469	0.635	0.056
Lack of external funding including government support	3.400	1.354	0.119	0.080	0.817
Bad economic situation	2.733	1.230	-0.071	0.063	0.814
Government pressure or interfere	2.667	1.213	0.456	0.152	0.708
Eigenvalue			4.546	1.651	1.314
% of variance			41.323	15.008	11.944
%cumulative variance			41.323	56.332	68.275
Number of components			4	4	3
Cronbach's a			.820	.815	.750

Note: KMO=.617; Bartlett's test of sphericity= 157.781; $s < .0005$

Table 6. Result of factor analysis for the 11 influential factors as barriers.

Many DPOs appear to have expanded their activities after making organisational changes. Twenty-five of the 32 respondents said they recently experienced changes in the management of their activities. Seven said they had not undergone any changes since their organisation had been established, and three of the seven admitted they needed some kind of managerial change. Of the 25 DPOs that had recently experienced managerial change, 15 said they had expanded the number and scale of their activities; six said they had downsized the number and scale of their activities; two said they had decreased the number of activities but intensified their focus on the remaining activities; and the other two said they had maintained the number of activities but expanded their activity scale.

With regard to the reasons for the DPO changes, the survey explored the causative factors of the changes in design promotion; however, the results are not statistically significant. Because each DPO deals with a unique set of conditions and circumstances, the crucial causative factors are likely to vary from

organisation to organisation. Further investigation is needed of the actual circumstances of each DPO in order to identify the key drivers of change and to determine why the change occurred. It is also necessary to analyse the consequences of the changes. Regardless of the positive and negative effects of change, such analysis could help other DPOs deal with similar causative factors and activities.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ACTIVITIES AND FACTORS

It is important to understand the relationship between activity priorities and influential factors with real contexts in order to provide better ways of managing the influential factors and activities. However, correlation analysis revealed that there are not strong correlations between each design promotion activity and the influential factors. It is assumed that the influential factors do not directly influence the activities themselves but those

Figure 5. A framework of design promotion activities with influential factors

influence organisations in their management of the activities. As a result of the influence, DPO may experience changes inside the organisation and those changes influence the management of the activities. Figure 5 shows the framework of the activities with the influential factors which explains this assumption. The Influential factors have two concepts. The first is factors that are considered importantly and the second is factors that are considered as barriers.

Those factors to consider and barrier factors obviously influence the DPOs in their management of activities. For example, as a result of the increasing amount of external fund, a DPO can hire more staff and they can enlarge their activities in counseling or advisory services to clients. However, if design awareness of their clients is very low and the clients are not aware of the value of design, the DPO will face to difficulties in their activities. They may need to manage certain activities that educate their clients to increase design awareness of the clients.

Likewise, it is important to understand what kind each DPO faces and how the influential factors actually influence the organisation with real contexts in order to manage the activities in strategic ways. Through the analysis of the survey, it was possible to identify what activities each DPO focuses on, what factors are importantly considered and what barriers influence the DPO. However, the social and economic context of each factors and how the factors influenced were not identified. Therefore, it will be necessary to understand the context with the consequences of the influences based on the proposed framework in the Figure 5.

FUTURE MANAGEMENT

In order to understand the change of the activity priorities in each DPO, the responses of each DPO on their current and future activities were analysed. The analysis revealed that 18 DPOs among 32 DPOs expected a change in the activity priorities in the near future. Other 14 DPOs expected that they will maintain the current focuses.

NEW DEMANDS FROM SOCIETY & PUBLIC SECTOR

Of the 18 DPOs that expect their priorities to change in the near future, 15 foresee a strengthening of design furtherance activities. Moreover, nine of the 14 DPOs that expect their priorities to remain the same anticipate a higher priority being placed on design furtherance activities. DPOs appear to have a growing awareness of the needs of society. The goal of design promotion has shifted. It is no longer focused exclusively on economic development but includes areas such as public services and social issues. Promoting design for public services and facilities is expected to be highlighted more and more because governments have a greater awareness of the impact of design on the sustainability of society and on the sustainable growth of national competitiveness. Addressing social issues or problems, such as aging, energy resources, and vandalism, is not a high priority in design promotion at the present time but could become a new challenge for the future.

STRATEGIC APPROACHES IN HELPING CLIENT COMPANIES

The focus of future design promotion appears to be on design encouragement, which includes activities such as education for corporate clients, the running of seminars and workshops, and the granting of design awards and certificates. Twelve of the 18 DPOs expect to focus more on the activities of design encouragement. Of these 12 DPOs, nine expect to have a dual focus on design encouragement and design furtherance. These results indicate that the creation of economic value and the development of industry are important design promotion objectives for the future. In open-ended questions, most DPOs mentioned the importance of helping SMEs to use design in a strategic way to enhance their relevant industries, including the design industry. In terms of future design promotion, the DPOs gave a low priority to design support activities such as giving direct design advice or financial support to clients. Instead, they favour activities that connect clients to appropriate designers or design firms or steer them towards design-related knowledge, such as a design knowledge centre.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

The aim of this research is to identify the relation between design promotion activities and the main factors in the management of design promotion so that DPOs can use the research results to evaluate their circumstances and manage their activities in more strategic ways. The report presents an analysis of the current practices and main factors of design promotion activities. The survey identifies the varied priorities of DPOs; it also identifies which factors are commonly viewed as important and which ones are viewed as barriers.

Most DPOs seem to have a common view on the importance of some particular factors, such as staff capabilities or the design awareness of clients, but diverse views on other factors, such as sustainable funding, self-generated income, and adherence to government policy. Factor analysis resulted in the identification of 11 barriers in the following three levels of design promotion: in-house problems; relationships with clients or other organisations; and environmental issues beyond the direct control of DPOs. The main factors that influence DPOs and cause organisational or managerial changes can be viewed as either high priorities or barriers.

In terms of future design promotion, most respondents foresee new demands arising from society and the public sector; they say more effort will be needed for researching and developing design policy, promoting public services, or addressing social problems. Most DPOs also acknowledge the growing importance of helping small and medium-sized enterprises to use design in a strategic way to enhance their industries, including the design industry.

FURTHER STUDY

However, this phenomenological analysis has a limitation. Consideration is not given to the actual social and economic circumstances of the DPOs. Further analysis of the specific circumstances of DPOs and their design promotion activities is therefore required for the purpose of proposing strategies for more effective management of design promotion.

And a better understanding is needed of the main factors that affect each DPO as well as the effects of social and economic circumstances. A chronological analysis has been planned for a select group of DPOs. The selection process will be based on the framework presented in Figure 5. The aim of the chronological analysis is to gain a better understanding of specific socioeconomic circumstances, particularly with regard to how those circumstances affect the way the DPOs manage their activities, how they deal with their high priority activities, and how they handle the key barriers.

Future analysis will focus on the success and failure of design promotion activities, particularly in light of the specific circumstances of each DPO. Micro-analysis of the DPO circumstances will provide an in-depth understanding of how DPOs successfully manage their activities and the main factors of design promotion. This understanding is expected to contribute to the sustainable growth of national competitiveness at the macro level.

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APPENDIX: LIST OF PARTICIPATED DESIGN PROMOTION ORGANISATIONS FOR SURVEY

Country	Organisation	Type	Year of Establishment
Argentina	Buenos Aires Metropolitan Design Center	Regional Government	2001
	DISEÑO+DISEÑO	Private Org.	1980
Belgium	Design Flanders	Regional Government	1965, 1991
	Flanders InShape	Regional Government	2007
Denmark	Danish Design Centre	Central Government	1978
Estonia	Estonian Design Center	Private, belongs to Universities & NGOs	2008
Finland	Design Forum Finland	Private	1875
France	APCI	Private Org.	1983
Hong Kong	Hong Kong Design Centre	Private org funded by Government	2001
Hungary	Hungarian Design Council	Central Government	2002
Ireland	Centre for Design Innovation	Belongs to University	2006
Japan	International Design Center Nagoya (IcdN)	Private org.	1992
	Osaka Design Center	Private org	1960
	Toyama Design Center	Regional Government	1999
	Japan Industrial Design Promotion Organisation (JIDPO)	Private, Belongs to the Government	1969
Korea	Korea Institute of Design Promoton (KIDP)	Central Government	1970
	Busan Design Center	Regional Government	2006
	Seoul Design Foundation	Regional Government	2009
	Gwangju Design Center	Regional Government	2005
	Daegu Design Center	Regional Government	2006
Malaysia	Malaysia Design Council	Central Government	1994
New Zealand	Better by Design	Central Government	2004
Norway	Norwegian Design Council	Central Government	1963
	Norsk Form	Private, funded by Government	1993
Poland	Institute of Industrial Design	Belongs to the State treasury	1950
Singapore	Design Singapore Council	Central Government	2004
Spain	Barcelona Design Centre	Private Org.	1973
Sweden	Svensk Form	Private Org.	1845
	Swedish Industrial Design Foundation	Private Org.	1989
Thailand	Thailand Creative & Design Center	Central Government	2005
United Kingdom	The Design Council	Private, belongs to the Government	1944
	Design Wales	Belongs to University	1994